

Devkant Theory of lines Addition

Discovery by Devkant Bishnoi

Devkant Bishnoi

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INTRODUCTION

First of all I want to tell you a very common thing that I noticed in calculator. You can clearly see that when we type any number in calculator we see numbers are written with a combination of several lines.

For example:

I understood and concluded that each number is made up of several lines.

Now let me explain you, as I told you before every number is made up of several lines .So I have written below the number of lines through the numbers are made of :

1 = 2 lines

2 = 5 lines

3 = 5 lines

4 = 4 lines

5 = 5 lines

6 = 6 lines

7 = 4 lines

8 = 7 lines

9 = 6 lines

0 = 6 lines

We got now our most important part for the upcoming discovery

Before starting the experiment,there are some conditions for performing this formula.

CONDITIONS

1. All numbers should be positive number
2. Numbers should not in fraction form
3. Numbers can be natural number, decimal numbers.

Lets start :

Let any numbers that you want to add:

$$576 + 257 = 833$$

576 = first number

257 = second number

833 = Result

Now, convert these numbers according to number of lines they have. (Given upside)

$$5 = 5, 7 = 4, 6 = 6, 2 = 5, 8 = 7, 3 = 5$$

$$546 + 554 = 755$$

546 = first converted number

554 = second converted

number

755 = Converted result

Now let use my rule:

Put all the values

$$(576+257+546+554) - (833+755) = (546+554) - 755$$

$$1933 - 1588 = 1100 - 755$$

$$345 = 345$$

Hence proved ✓

My contact information

My name = Devkant Bishnoi

My father name = Mahender Singh

My mother name = Suman Devi

My mobile no = 9253150633

Father mobile no = 9215550633

My address = Sadalpur,Hisar, Haryana,India

My age = 16 years

Gmail = devkantbishnoi4@gmail.com

These numbers have also available whatsapp so you can also contact on whatsapp

Please contact me if you found and understand my theorem